

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Centre for Data, Culture & Society

CDCS ANNUAL REPORT

2024-2025

2024-2025

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HELLO!

WELCOME TO THE SIXTH ANNUAL REPORT OF THE CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY.

This report presents the range of our activities and the projects we have supported across the academic year 2024/25. It shows the ways in which, as we adapt to changing contexts and demands, the Centre continues to focus on strengthening our core mission of holding an inclusive and innovative space for building capacity in responsible data-led and digital research in the arts, humanities and social sciences. With our roots now well-established, this year we have been able to branch out into newer directions, contributing to national conversations around the future of the UK's digital research infrastructure, leading the way locally and nationally in responsible research practices.

Highlights this year have included achieving over 1000 registrations for our training programme; our Annual Lecture, given by Alex Gil of Yale University, which focused on the realities and politics of 'best practice' in the Digital Humanities; and seeing the team being invited to participate in projects and deliver a number of talks on our work both nationally and internationally. Our Digital Research Prizes are always a particular high point in the spring, with awards this year going to people from seven different disciplines within the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. We were also delighted at the success of our Digital Research Analyst who was awarded a DISKAH fellowship to work on a project on improving OCR errors through high performance compute.

The core values of CDCS – community, collaboration, inclusivity - continue to underpin all our work. This report is a testament to the team work and many hands that build networks and activities that intersect and reinforce one another: we are deeply proud of the canopy that the Centre now forms, nurturing our research and learning communities, as they themselves branch out into data-led and applied computational methods. As always, we look forward with excitement to seeing how their ideas and skills will grow.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

CDCS continues to benefit from the energy, commitment and enthusiasm of a highly skilled and highly productive team: thanks are due to Lucia Michielin, Jessica Witte, Likando Kumoyo, Emily Allan, Ed McKenzie and Alexis Pister.

Our Advisory Board was chaired this year by Dr Ben Moews, who provided thoughtful leadership and support. Thanks also go to the other members of the board, particularly those leaving us this year: Emily Postan; Tim Epple; Alex Chow; Phil Sheail; as well as our three PhD Reps – Rhys, Ari and Ash, who have been great supporters of the Centre throughout their PhDs. The board's insights and perspectives are crucial in shaping our work and the support we provide to the CAHSS research community. In July our Data Visualisation Engineer Alexis Pister left to take up an academic post: we wish him luck and happiness as he moves forward with his career.

DR LISA OTTY

Director

CDCS PEOPLE

LISA OTTY
DIRECTOR

LUCIA MICHELIN
Digital Research Skills
Training Manager

ED MACKENZIE
Research Technologist

JESSICA WITTE
Digital Research Analyst

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CDCS Events and
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Data Visualisation Engineer

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Founding Director, Professor
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School of Economics

ORIAN BROOK
School of Social and Political
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PhD Representative

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School of Divinity

RHYS DAVIES
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School of Informatics

REBECCA HIRSCH
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School of History, Classics
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Advisory Board Chair,
Business School

BENJAMIN MOLINEAUX
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Psychology and Language
Sciences

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Edinburgh College of Art

EMILY POSTAN
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Education and Sport

ARI STILLMAN
PhD Representative

NEW PHD AFFILIATES

BHAVINEE SINGH
School of Law

PHD AFFILIATES

VICTORIA EVANS
Edinburgh College of Art

ROXANNE GUILFORD
School of History, Classics and
Archaeology

YILI
School of Literatures, Languages
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NAOMI KORN
School of Literatures, Languages
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AYÇA ATABEY
School of Law

**FRANCISCA ANITA ADOM-
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School of Social and Political Science

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ALBERT SHARRA
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ASH CHARLTON
School of History, Classics and
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**CLAUDIA GONZÁLEZ-
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MARTIN CHENG
Business School

ARI STILLMAN
School of Social and Political Science

GRAHAM SKEATE
Edinburgh College of Art

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Research Associate
University of Sheffield Digital
Humanities Institute (DHI)

ALEXANDRA HUANG-KOKINA
Postdoctoral Digital Research Fellow
Institute for Advanced Studies in the
Humanities, University of Edinburgh

EVENTS

BRINGING PEOPLE TOGETHER

Building community and networks among those using digital research methods is an important part of our work: giving people the chance to meet others with similar interests, inspiring researchers and ensuring that our community has opportunities to hear from leading scholars. Over the years, the team has also built up our own expertise, and this year we were delighted to be able to share our work in a number of different venues.

The Point is Still To Change It: On Doing Better Than Best Practices in Data Work for Culture and Society
Alex Gil

This year's annual lecture was delivered by Professor Alex Gil, of Yale University. *The Point is Still To Change It: On Doing Better Than Best Practices in Data Work for Culture and Society*, explored a range of projects to

examine how best practices can "serve as little else than alibis for rigid hierarchies and the imposition of North Atlantic forms of being that take for granted rich computational infrastructures" and how the Digital Humanities community might aim for 'better than best' in future.

SEMINAR SERIES

THE SYSTEMS WHICH GOVERN US

Madhumita Murgia & Georgina Voss

OPEN METHODS FOR DIGITAL CONSERVATION OF HISTORIC MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

Matthew Hamilton

WIKIDATA, BIOGRAPHICAL LIVES, AND LINKED INFRASTRUCTURES OF WOMEN'S WORK 1870-1950

James Baker

THE POLITICS OF NUMBERS: QUEER DATA AND THE COUNTING OF LGBTQ COMMUNITIES

Kevin Guyan

GETTING STARTED WITH TRANSKRIBUS

Joe Nockels

RECONSTRUCTING THE ROMAN TRANSPORT NETWORK: NEW METHODS AND APPROACHES TO MODELLING MOBILITY FROM THE R3URBN PROJECT

Andrew McLean

RESPONSIBLE INNOVATION IN CREATIVE AI: EARLY FINDINGS FROM THE CREA-TEC PROJECT

Caterina Moruzzi

CDCS SUPPORTED EVENTS

Creative Digital Dynamics II: Symposium on AI & Digital Innovations for Voice and Vocal Music

IASH Digital Research Postdoctoral Fellow Alexandra Huang-Kokina, whose fellowship CDCS supports, was given funding to host a conference that brought together scholars across her research field.

Back of the Envelope

Martha Bohm, a PhD student at ESALA, received CDCS funding to host a workshop on how architects are using digital tools to respond to the climate crisis.

The Digital Museum Conference

We supported our colleague Professor Arkotong Longkumer to host this event arising out of his Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) project, *Decolonising the Museum: Digital Repatriation of the Gaidinliu Collection from the UK to India* (DiMuse).

Culture is Bad for You

Culture is Bad for You, written by CDCS Advisory Board member Orian Brook and colleagues, offers a powerful call to transform the cultural and creative industries by examining the intersections between race, class and gender inequalities in cultural occupations. This event marked the publication of a new, updated edition of the book. The authors and scholars from around the world discussed the mechanisms of exclusion in cultural work and how they are mirrored in other national and policy contexts.

TEAM TALKS

DIGITAL AND COMPUTATIONAL METHODS FOR HERITAGE \ LECTURE

Lucia Michielin, *Inclusive Community Building through Digital Heritage Preservation in Times of Crisis: Strategies for Cohesive Resilience in the Face of War, Migration, and Climate Change* (University of St Andrews and Charles University, Czech Republic)

FAILURE IN DIGITAL HUMANITIES \ KEYNOTE PANEL

Lisa Otty, UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association Conference (University of Glasgow)

GREENING YOUR DIGITAL RESEARCH \ WORKSHOP

Lisa Otty, Digital Research Conference (University of Edinburgh)

IS OPEN DATA REALLY OPEN? THE HANSARD PARLIAMENTARY DATA CASE STUDY \ CONFERENCE PAPER

Lucia Michielin, Jessica Witte and Kenneth Fordyce, DH2025, Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal)

MIND THE GAP! SUPPORTING CODE-FREE COMPUTATIONAL RESEARCH THROUGH SMALL SCALE APPS \ CONFERENCE PAPER

Lucia Michielin, DH2025, Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal)

GENERATIVE AI FOR OCR ERROR CORRECTION: A CASE STUDY OF HISTORICAL NEWSPAPER ARCHIVES \ CONFERENCE PAPER

Jessica Witte, DH2025, Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal)

TOWARDS A EUROPEAN AND UK DIGITAL HUMANITIES INFRASTRUCTURE \ CONFERENCE PAPER

Lisa Otty and Giota Alevizou (KCL), Digital Humanities Congress 2024 (University of Sheffield)

LEGAL AND ETHICAL CHALLENGES OF WEB SCRAPING IN THE DIGITAL HUMANITIES \ CONFERENCE PAPER

Jessica Witte and Lucia Michielin, UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association Conference (University of Glasgow)

FIKAS & SOCIALS

Digital research is often interdisciplinary, and it can be hard to meet those working with the same methods in other disciplines. To help, we hold regular get-togethers including 'fikas' (coffee mornings), socials and of course community events such as the Digital Research Prizes award ceremony. Everyone is welcome to come along and join our welcoming network!

"I THOUGHT ALEX GIL'S TALK WAS BRILLIANT AND INSPIRING, A REALLY FRESH AND RADICAL APPROACH TO TACKLING THE CORPORATE WORLD."
ANNUAL LECTURE ATTENDEE

"EXCELLENT PRESENTATION BY THE SPEAKER, DEPTH OF KNOWLEDGE AND ABILITY TO SHARE INSIGHTS MADE IT A VERY ENGAGING TALK."
SEMINAR SERIES ATTENDEE

TRAINING

SHARING OUR METHODS

Our training was as popular as ever this year, with hundreds of researchers continuing to benefit from a range of courses, including new offerings focused on incorporating artificial intelligence and large language models into research practice. As always, all our courses were developed and delivered by our talented team of Training Fellows, who join us from across the University bringing a diverse mix of skills and research experience.

CDCS TRAINING COURSES: 48

CDCS TRAINING REGISTRATIONS: 1003

TRAINING PROGRAMME

This year, our training offer was streamlined to a core programme of 48 courses and workshops, which attracted 1003 registrations over two semesters. Courses ranged from structured and unstructured data analysis to GIS and, for the first time, the use of AI and LLMs in research.

SHARING OUR MATERIALS

Our GitHub page now hosts 91 repositories contributed by 44 people. All of our repositories are covered by a CC-BY-NC 4.0 licence to encourage reusability. These repositories can be easily navigated through both title-based and thematic searches. Additionally, this page now features three comprehensive tutorials focused on best practices in digital research and structured data analysis, with more resources forthcoming.

OUR CORE TOPICS

- Digitised documents & text analysis
- Intro to programming for researchers
- Data wrangling & data visualisation
- Structured data analysis
- Geographical data
- Artificial Intelligence
- Good practices of digital research

CDCS TRAINING FELLOWS 24/25

AISLINN KEOGH

Aislinn is a PhD student in the Centre for Language Evolution. Her research combines behavioural experiments and agent-based modelling to investigate the role of language production biases in the emergence of linguistic structure. She is proficient in Python, R and JavaScript and is passionate about the use of simulation-based techniques for experimental design and data analysis.

BRIAN TSZ HO WONG

Brian Tsz Ho Wong is a PhD candidate (East Asian Studies) in the School of Literatures, Languages & Cultures. His research explores the networks of capital and power elites in the wartime Japanese Empire, and the use of private capital to fuel imperial ambitions. He is passionate about using digital tools (Gephi, QGIS and Google Earth) in his research. At CDGS, he is excited to teach and support the use of Gephi in humanities and interdisciplinary studies.

CHRIS OLDNALL

Chris is a PhD mathematics researcher with the MAC-MIGS Centre of Doctoral Training, who is affiliated with the Institute of Genetics and Cancer. His work is interdisciplinary and involves combining causal inference with genomics. He loves teaching individuals on how to get the most out of 'big data' by using analysis techniques appropriately and accurately, and most importantly how to implement these in Python and R.

FANG JACKSON-YANG

Fang Jackson-Yang is based in the School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences. Fang researches how people communicate prominent information in transitive events. She uses eye-tracking techniques to investigate when and how listeners make predictions of the endpoints of such events. She also uses laboratory and digital corpus data to investigate how speakers use various sentence structures and other linguistic means to describe such events in different settings and what factors influence their choices.

KI TONG

Ki is a PhD candidate at the Advanced Care Research Centre studying ways to enhance greenspace accessibility for older adults. She is a landscape architect with professional experience delivering construction projects and landscape assessments. Besides an interest in using QGIS and ArcGIS for geospatial visualisation and analysis, she expanded her exploration with aggregating geospatial data and performing further analysis with R to study the correlation between environmental variables and urban density.

MARTIN DISLEY

Martin Disley is a practice-led design researcher based at the Institute for Design Informatics at the University of Edinburgh. His critical engineering studio practice blends artistic inquiry and investigative computing, producing outputs in software, film, installation and text. His PhD research explores adversarial design and investigative aesthetics as Research through Design methods for explainability and interpretability of generative computer vision.

RHYS DAVIES

Rhys is a psychologist based at the School of Health in Social Sciences where he is researching adaptive behaviours and mental health in elite sports. His research makes use of statistical modelling with survey data, particularly investigating interactions to determine how context shapes the efficacy of "adaptive" behaviours. His preferred coding language is R, and he is passionate about using data visualisation techniques to communicate and simplify research findings.

SARAH SCHÖTTLER

Sarah Schöttler is a PhD candidate at the VisHub lab in the School of Informatics. Her research explores responsive visualization with a focus on geographic data and visualization. She is active in the visualization community and has previously worked as a visualisation and map developer for clients such as the PeaceRep consortium at the Edinburgh Law School. At CDGS, she is excited to teach and offer support with data visualization and mapping, web development and general programming skills.

XAN COCHRAN

Xan Cochran (they/them) is a Research Masters' student in Informatics, with supervisors in Informatics and Philosophy. Their research concerns the metaphysics of 'levels' in scientific discourses, and combines philosophical analysis with the computational modelling of epistemic communities. They hold degrees in English Literature and Developmental Linguistics, and have for the last decade been working as a tutor in schools across the University.

“ONE ASPECT OF THIS COURSE THAT I THOUGHT WAS PARTICULARLY WELL DONE WAS THE HANDS-ON APPROACH. RATHER THAN SPENDING TOO MUCH TIME ON THEORY, WE WERE ENCOURAGED TO GET INVOLVED AND START PRACTISING STRAIGHT AWAY. I FOUND THIS TO BE A HIGHLY EFFECTIVE WAY OF LEARNING, AS IT ALLOWED US TO ENGAGE WITH THE MATERIAL ACTIVELY. THROUGH THE EXERCISES, I INEVITABLY PICKED UP NEW KNOWLEDGE, SOMETIMES EVEN WITHOUT REALISING IT AT FIRST.”

PARTICIPANT \ TRAINING PROGRAMME 2024-25

SKILLS

WE'RE ALWAYS LEARNING

Our skill development offer doesn't end with our training programme: as well as collaborating with partners to support other learning events, we create online resources such as our self-guided pathways, offer one-to-one clinics and bursaries and support sandpits and hacks. This year we've also been taking time to reflect on our own teaching and training practice, as part of our local digital research community.

REFLECTING ON HOW WE TEACH

In January, we participated in the Pair Programming Winter School, where we reflected on the advantages and limitations of using server-based tools for teaching coding. In February, we organised a round table at the University of Edinburgh’s Digital Research Conference, further exploring the theme of empowering non-coders. These discussions have been instrumental in shaping our contributions to the forthcoming book *Teaching Programming Across Disciplines*, where our chapters focus on developing a coding mindset, crafting teaching materials in multiple languages, creating strategies for online teaching, fostering interdisciplinarity through our Training Programme and overcoming technological barriers.

SUPPORTING DATA SKILLS ACROSS THE UNIVERISTY

SACHA PROGRAMME

This year, we continued to support the challenge-based Students as Change Agents (SACHA) programme, which brings together students from different subjects to solve real-world problems with a wider social, environmental, or economic impact. We mentored the SACHA Data Coaches as they provided data support and computational methods development for students.

DATALAB ACADEMY

The Data Lab Academy’s (TDLA) Innovation Week is a three-day programme where Data Science students across Scotland are invited to participate in real-world complex challenges whilst learning about the required tools and perspectives for successful co-design. The CDCS data coach compiled and organised data from industry-based partners into a user-friendly data playground for the attendees, as well as providing technical and methodological support.

HCA SHOWCASE

We delivered a deep dive workshop to support PhDs from the School of History, Classics & Archaeology in navigating digital research. During the event, we provided the attendees with an overview of the digital and computational methods that are most relevant to historical and archaeological research. We also demonstrated the practical application of computational tools to analysing historical documents.

VERSION CONTROL FOR RESEARCH DATA SCOTLAND

This year, we conducted our first bespoke workshop for an EFI partner, Research Data Scotland. The workshop centred on enhancing collaborative workflows using the Git version control system, in conjunction with the widely-used online platform GitHub and the GitHub Desktop application. Through hands-on examples, participants learned how to leverage the GitHub Desktop app for streamlined version control and collaboration. Additionally, we explored GitHub’s interface to maximise the benefits of accessing and utilising openly shared data, code, scripts and documents effectively.

FESTIVALS DATA SANDPIT

EFI builds collaborative partnerships within key local sectors, including festivals and tourism. To support this, we held a research sandpit focused on data shared by festival partners and gathered from open sources. Researchers explored what insights they could draw from ticketing data, memberships and event listings. A number of participants have subsequently developed their ideas into small projects.

SUPPORTING EFI STUDENTS

This year, we designed challenge-led skills training for EFI students. “Digital and Computational Methods for Research” offered an overview of the principal challenges and opportunities in digital research, introduced key methods and techniques and provided a practical demonstration using historical data. The second event, the “Text Analysis and the Humanities” workshop, introduced the fundamental concepts of computational text analysis. Participants explored material and code to analyse the Scottish Statistical Accounts, thereby observing computational methods in practice.

SELF-PACED AND ONLINE LEARNING

Since not everyone learns in the same way or has the same amount of time available, we provide training in forms that are both diverse and flexible. This also increases the reusability and accessibility of our materials, ensuring that they can reach a wide range of learners. To this end, we have identified a selection of training materials that can form self-contained online resources, and we have already published the first three in this format.

MAKE YOUR STATISTICAL ANALYSIS REPRODUCIBLE (FROM SPSS TO R)

A practical introduction to converting statistical analyses from SPSS to R, demonstrating how to perform common tasks—from data manipulation and visualisation to statistical testing and APA-style reporting—within R.

SHARE YOUR RESEARCH RESULTS WITH INTERACTIVE APPLICATIONS (SHINY)

An overview of how to build interactive web applications in R using Shiny, emphasising how such apps enable users to explore data and analysis processes dynamically rather than passively.

INTRODUCTION TO BAYESIAN STATISTICS

An introduction to the principles of Bayesian statistics, highlighting how the framework differs from frequentist approaches by asking, “What is the probability of different hypotheses, given the data and our prior beliefs about the world?”

TRAINING BURSARIES

RADIOCARBON DATING AND BAYESIAN CHRONOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

This year, we helped Dr Sam Leggett attend a short course in Radiocarbon Dating and Bayesian Chronological Analysis at the University of Oxford.

ESSEX SUMMER SCHOOL IN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ANALYSIS

We sent Mukti Ratna Dewi to the Essex Summer School in Social Science Data Analysis - 2N Geospatial Data and Spatial Analysis.

PROJECTS

MOVING RESEARCH FORWARD.

Interdisciplinary digital and data-led research is rarely a solo effort. We continue to cultivate a community where innovative ideas are supported and where collaboration enriches the University's research culture. In 2024–25, we supported a wide range of projects from early-stage planning and proposal development to post-award technical development.

PROJECTS

CDCS DIGITAL RESEARCH SANDPITS

The CDCS Digital Research Sandpit offers support to researchers at the early stages of their projects in developing prototypes or proofs of concept. Sandpit participants can also receive small project funding to support the purchase of relevant datasets, software or equipment, or the time of research assistants. This year, we were pleased to see two prototypes evolve into full-scale projects:

DR ROCHELLE ROWE, 'PERFORMATIVE BLACKNESS AND BLACK HISTORIES IN SCOTLAND'

How was Blackness represented and performed onstage in Scotland between 1839 and 1939? Dr Rochelle Rowe, Lecturer in the School of History, Classics & Archaeology, explores this question through a decolonial lens in her AHRC Catalyst-funded project set to begin later this year. Rochelle is investigating how Blackness was staged in both professional and amateur contexts, and how these performances contributed to constructions of race and identity in Scotland. A key output of her work will be a public-facing digital database hosted on the project website. During the 2023 Rapid Prototyping Sandpit, CDCS supported Rochelle in honing her project idea and developing the data architecture for the database. We look forward to continuing our collaboration by providing research technology support throughout the project.

DR KENNETH FORDYCE, UK PARLIAMENT DISCOURSE ON IMMIGRATION (2007–2024)

Dr Kenneth Fordyce, Senior Lecturer in Language Education, is investigating how discourse around immigration has changed in UK parliamentary debates since 2007. Supported by our technical team, Dr Fordyce extracted parliamentary transcripts from the Hansard Parliamentary Debates Archive related to migration and asylum. Dr Fordyce plans to use text analysis methods from computational linguistics to explore the dataset, which will become a proof-of-concept for a database tracking political discourse on immigration. Early findings were presented in two conference papers this summer and have paved the way for what, we hope, will be a successful funding bid supporting Dr Fordyce in scaling up the project.

IASH FELLOWSHIPS 2024–25

Digital Visiting Research Fellow

DR ARTUR R. BOELDERL

The Book Not to Come: How Digitization Affects Literary Research and Text Theory

Digital Research Postdoctoral Fellow

DR STEPHANIE LAMPREA

A Feminist Digital Voice in Electroacoustic Music and Interdisciplinary Performance Art

Digital Research Postdoctoral Fellow

DR ALEXANDRA HUANG-KOKINA

Artificial 'Emotional' Intelligence for Opera Theatre: Innovating audience engagement in contemporary science-fiction opera

DISKAH FELLOWSHIP

Jessica Witte, CDCS Digital Research Analyst, was awarded a fellowship from the Digital Skills in the Arts & Humanities (DISKAH) Network. Over the course of the year-long fellowship, she is developing a workflow using fine-tuned large language models (LLMs) to correct complex OCR errors in *The Scotsman* newspaper archive. She is also creating resources to support arts & humanities researchers using high-performance computing (HPC) infrastructure such as the University's Eddie cluster.

DIGITAL RESEARCH FUND PROJECTS

We have a rolling open call for applications to our Digital Research Fund, which can cover software and hardware costs, the cost of technical help, and other research-related expenses. This year, we supported 7 researchers in purchasing hardware, acquiring datasets, hiring technical staff, and showcasing their work.

- Pip Thornton: Machine Whispers
- Alexandra Huang-Kokina: Oper-AI: Innovating Audience Engagement and Participation in Immersive Opera
- Will Zhang: Does Simulated Spending Increase Actual Spending on Virtual Goods?
- Martha Bohm: Back of the Envelope.
- Wang Tong: Shadow Influencer: A Generative AI-Based Content Creator Assistant
- Susan Lechelt: Cultivating Calm: Using Technology to Bridge Urban Isolation, Slow Down and Reconnect with Nature
- Dayu Sari: Enhancing the Capacity of Blue and Green Infrastructure to Develop Cultural Ecosystem Service: Case Study of Jakarta Metropolitan Area, Indonesi

COLLABORATION

LENDING OUR HANDS.

As we build capacity for digital research, we collaborate across our sector in order to develop infrastructure and skills, explore responsible research practice and share knowledge and expertise. Our collaborative work this year has focused on a few key strands: digital research infrastructure, research software engineering capacity, digital sustainability and the skills needed in the arts and humanities to engage effectively in our increasingly digital society.

COLLABORATION

DIGITAL HUMANITIES CLIMATE COALITION

NEW DHCC PUBLICATION

Interpreting UKRI Environmental Sustainability Guidance for the Digital Humanities is a short guide aimed primarily at digital humanities researchers and research offices that explores the policy resources underpinning the AHRC's sustainability statement. This publication offers a series of interpretations of existing guidance on sustainable research practice and points to advice on how to operationalise this guidance in DH research.

TALKS AND WORKSHOPS

The DHCC community continues to meet monthly online, and we frequently share the toolkit and the card game based on it with research and cultural organisations. This year, we held workshops at the UK-Ireland DH Association conference in Glasgow, at the Digital Research conference in Edinburgh and as part of our RSE Summer School in London.

DIGITAL SUSTAINABILITY CARD GAME

Over the last couple of years, members of the DHCC have created a card game based on the contents of the DHCC Toolkit. In small groups, players act as organisations competing against (or perhaps collaborating with) the others to become more digitally sustainable. The toolkit contains an accessible guide to running a DHCC Workshop based on the Sustainability Card Game. We have shared this game with students, conference delegates and software developers and have received great feedback.

TOWARD A NEW CCP FOR ARTS, HUMANITIES, AND CULTURE RESEARCH

We are participating in the advisory group for a new scoping project led by Eamonn Bell (University of Durham). This project is exploring what a new Collaborative Computational Project (CCP) for the Arts, Humanities, and Culture (AH&C) research community could look like. With humanities researchers increasingly dependent on all aspects of digital research infrastructure (DRI)—including skills development, compute platforms, software techniques and the sustainable use of AI and HPC—this collaborative project will lead to the first network of its kind to support the AHRC research community, and will have a significant impact nationally and internationally. The first CCP-AH Townhall was held in Durham in May 2025.

RSE CAPABILITIES FRAMEWORK

Our team includes a number of research software engineers (RSEs) who combine technical expertise with a deep knowledge of research practices and the unique complexities of humanities data. The RSE role is increasingly recognised as a vital one in research delivery, and we actively support the development of humanities-specific RSE training and career pathways. As part of this work, we contributed to a panel at the annual UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association conference titled 'Giving a Digital Humanities Voice to the Research Technical Professionals Skills Framework'. The panel was organised by Phil Reed (University of Manchester), an SSI Fellow currently developing the application of the DIRECT Framework to Digital Humanities.

AIHUMS101

Along with colleagues in Digital Education, CDCS is participating in the Una Europa project *Artificial Intelligence & Humanities (101): Developing a Humanities Syllabus for AI & the Digital*. Led by Cillian Ó Fathaigh (Jagiellonian University, Poland), with partners in Bologna, Edinburgh, Dublin, Leiden, Madrid and Leuven, the project will explore what students need in order to engage effectively with AI and digital technologies. The project is producing a survey on current teaching within Una Europa, a model syllabus of an introductory course to AI and the digital for humanities students and a toolkit for integrating AI into existing courses.

RSE SUMMER SCHOOL

As co-organisers of the UK's DH RSE Summer School, which is aimed at postgraduate students, researchers and other professionals in Digital Humanities and allied sectors who wish to learn more about careers and best practices in Research Software Engineering, we contributed a day of training focused on environmental sustainability. Sustainability is key to good software engineering—not just in planning, maintaining and sharing software, but also in developing environmentally responsible computing practices that reduce the impact of digital research on the world. This event was organised by CDCS, King's Digital Lab, Cambridge Digital Humanities and the DISKAH Network, with funding from Strategic Technical Platform for University Technical Professionals (STEP-UP) and the UK Society of Research Software Engineering.

INFRASTRUCTURE

CREATING STRONG FOUNDATIONS

Digital research relies on a range of platforms and services which operate at varying scales from institutional to international. We work to ensure our community has access to the infrastructure they need and that their perspectives can feed into the development of future infrastructure. We also host, develop and maintain services, prioritising open source software and projects and community-led initiatives.

SUPPORTING COMMUNITIES OF DIGITAL RESEARCH PRACTICE

TEI

We continue to host a TEI service on existDB, and this year have developed a digital edition project using TEI publisher: if you are interest in discussing support for a TEI project, please get in touch.

VIS MEET UPS

Our Data Visualisation Engineer has hosted Edinburgh Vis meet ups at EFI to bring the local visualisation community together.

OMEKA SERVICE

Over the last year we have been exploring the potential of Omeka as a platform for a variety of projects, including collections and exhibitions.

CDCS SHINY APPS

Non-coding tools have expanded accessibility in digital humanities, empowering researchers without programming skills. However, there are often gaps that prevent researchers from completing an entire digital pipeline solely with GUI-based tools. To address this, we have launched a new page introducing Shiny apps designed to bridge these gaps. The first app available is a Data Transformation Tool, which helps convert datasets between .txt and .csv formats, making it easier to prepare data for cleaning and analysis across different software platforms.

DARIAH

We manage the University of Edinburgh's institutional cooperating partnership with DARIAH. On Tuesday 3 September 2024, UK DARIAH Day was held in Leeds, where the UK cooperating partners of DARIAH (the Universities of Brighton, Edinburgh, Exeter and Leeds, Kings College London and the School of Advanced Study, University of London) came together to consider the opportunities and challenges around research infrastructures in the UK and how closer alignment with DARIAH EU can strengthen ongoing UK efforts.

PROG HIST

We continue our institutional partnership with the Programming Historian, whose material forms the basis of our silent disco training format. The Programming Historian has been translating tutorials into a range of languages over the last year, and we are proud to be associated with this work which opens digital scholarship up internationally.

TRANSKRIBUS

As founding members of the READ COOP and institutional members of Transkribus, we can offer our researchers enhanced access and credits for this AI-powered HTR (handwritten text recognition) software. We're pleased to see increasing use of Transkribus across the community. Please get in touch if you want to find out about the support we can offer.

DIGITAL RESEARCH PRIZES

CELEBRATING OUTSTANDING RESEARCH

It is always a great pleasure to host our annual celebration of digital research, the CDCS Digital Research Prizes. Open to researchers across the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the prizes this year showcased projects large and small that use digital methods to address diverse research questions, including work on poverty premiums, barriers to education, national security, online safety and LLMs. Awards are presented at a ceremony in May, which makes a lovely moment to bring the CDCS community together.

BEST SMALL DATA-DRIVEN PROJECT

WINNER

MEASURING THE ENERGY POVERTY PREMIUM IN GREAT BRITAIN AND IDENTIFYING ITS MAIN DRIVERS BASED ON LONGITUDINAL HOUSEHOLD SURVEY DATA

Fiona Rasanga, Tina Harrison and Raffaella Calabrese

“This project’s findings make a strong contribution to better understanding fuel poverty in the UK, which will hopefully positively impact policy decisions in the future.”

Highly Commended

Utilising social media data and text analysis: corporate leaders’ social and environmental information dissemination

Mengjing Li, Shuo Wang and Yue (Lucy) Liu

Highly Commended

Data Doppelganger

Sarah Immel, Beatrice Alex and Susan Lechelt

BEST DATA VISUALISATION

WINNER

PATHS IN EDUCATION

Paula Lago and Stuart King

“This visualisation effectively and accessibly provides a compelling snapshot of the difficulties young people in Uruguay face in completing their education. The visualisation itself is not only creative, but it also contributes to shaping the narrative.”

BEST DATASET

WINNER

NATIONAL SECURITY AND DEFENCE DOCUMENTS DATASET (1987–2024)

Andrew Neal and Roy Gardner

“A high-quality, well-documented dataset that will be of interest to many researchers and teachers at the University and beyond.”

BEST IMPACT FROM A DATA-LED PROJECT

WINNER

EQUALLY SAFE ONLINE (ESO)

Poppy Gerrard-Abbott, Fiona McNeil, Ioannis Konstas, Christine McMello, Claire Houghto, Gavin Abercrombi, Tanvi Dinka, Simone Frennd, Aiqi Jian and Nancie Gunson

“This project is poised to make a significant contribution in addressing gender-based harassment and violence online, and the approach could also more generally intervene in addressing many negative phenomena on social media such as the spread of misinformation.”

Highly Commended

Data Education in Schools - Escape Rooms

Judy Robertson, Kate Farrell, Jasmeen Kanwal, Antonia Sewell, Jo Spiller, Serdar Abaci, Tommy Lawson, Giovanna Pasquariello and Angela Hunter

BEST NOVEL USE OF A DIGITAL METHOD

WINNER

DO OR DO NOT: LLM UNDERSTANDINGS OF COLLECTIVE VS INDIVIDUAL ACTION

Ari Stillman

“This exploratory study not only tests the method itself, but does so through a ‘no-code’ pipeline that makes computational research more accessible to those with various levels of digital literacy.”

DATA

METRICS THAT MATTER

Our numbers have held steady this year, despite a challenging context locally. Our community continues to develop new projects and use our services. We have had another bumper year for training, whilst streamlining the programme and saving some costs. We have also focused less on social media this year, leaving Twitter and moving most of our events communications to Bluesky and local channels, including our mailing list which continues to grow apace.

AUDIENCE

- US 10.05%
- India 3.63%
- China 2.76%
- Germany 2.55%
- Other 23.3%
- UK 57.71% (Edinburgh 22.22%)

Breakdown of the top geographic locations of our web audience

14
PHD
AFFILIATES

3435
MAILING LIST
SUBSCRIBERS

12
RESEARCH
ASSOCIATES

16
SANDPIT
APPLICATIONS

2
TRAINING
BURSARIES

23
DATA
SURGERIES

1466
DOWNLOADS
OF OUR ZENODO
PUBLICATIONS

13
RESEARCH
PROJECTS
SUPPORTED

91
TRAINING
MATERIAL
REPOSITORIES

WEBSITE

Total number of visitors

Total number of page views

2,604
Returning visitors to website

EVENTS

Total number of events

Total number of registrations

Almost 600 people registered to attend the 28 events that CDCS hosted in 24/25.

BUDGET AUGUST 2024 / JULY 2025 BREAKDOWN

TOTAL SPEND £299K

- Staff £239.2K
- Events £11.5K
- Bursaries & Scholarships £14.6K
- Projects £9K
- Training £19.5K
- Other £5.2K

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@EDCDCS

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CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY

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